

FLAME NEWSLETTER – ISSUE 3

National Observatory of Athens

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FLAME is a research project carried out at the Institute for Environmental Research and Sustainable Development (IERSD) of the National Observatory of Athens (NOA). The overarching goal of the project is the study and characterization of the environmental conditions that promote extreme wildfires in Greece, intending to increase awareness and enhance the preparedness of fire operatives and the public.

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Editorial

Welcome to **Issue 3** of FLAME's e-Newsletter!

In the aftermath of the catastrophic 2021 fire season, during which more than 100,000 ha of land was destroyed in Greece, our research team continued working hard to produce new knowledge to increase awareness and enhance preparedness for extreme fire weather and fire behavior. Our project recorded significant progress over the preceding months. We accomplished and published the first promotional video of FLAME, talking about weather and wildfires to highlight the important role that fire meteorology can play in preventing and suppressing wildfires. Further, we moved on to define the so-called critical fire weather patterns of Greece, linking synoptic meteorological patterns with different levels of fire danger and/or potential for producing extreme fire behavior. Very soon, the results of this research task will be codified in the form of a handbook that will be communicated to all interested stakeholders, aspiring to be an additional tool in the effort to better prepare and protect Greece against wildfires.

FLAME's third newsletter is thus dedicated to what our research team achieved in the previous period, including dissemination actions both inside and outside the scientific community. In this issue, you will also read about the science of pyrometeorology and the role of lightning concerning wildfires.

Enjoy reading!

Theodore M. Giannaros
Principal Investigator of FLAME
IERSD/NOA
15.07.2022

PYROMETEOROLOGY

Pyrometeorology is a branch of meteorology that deals specifically with how weather affects the ignition, spread, and behavior of wildfires, but also with how fire creates its own weather. Meteorological conditions prevailing in an area are a factor that can interact with each of the fundamental elements that define the ignition and behavior of fire (see image above). For instance, wind carries the oxygen necessary to sustain combustion, while temperature, relative humidity, and solar radiation affect the rate at which fuels dry. Due to their effect on fire ignition and spread, the set of associated meteorological variables is more often referred to as “**fire weather**”.

Early fire weather research identified quickly **4 key elements** capable of promoting the occurrence of large and potentially catastrophic wildfires. These elements are atmospheric **moisture**, **wind**, atmospheric **stability**, and **drought**.

The availability of water in the atmosphere (**humidity**) is a key fire weather element with a significant effect on fire danger and fire behavior. In general, **low humidity increases the flammability of fuels**, making them easier to ignite and carry fire. The prevalence of dry conditions can also increase significantly firefront intensity, rate of spread, and the likelihood of spotting.

Wind is perhaps the most studied fire weather element. Its role in fire ignition and behavior is multi-dimensional since it contributes to the **exchange of moisture** between fuels and the atmosphere, directly affects the **rate of fire spread**, promotes the **production** and **transport** of **burning embers** (spotting), and controls the **flow of oxygen** and other combustion products.

Atmospheric stability is a fire weather element that is closely related to fire behavior. As a meteorological term, stability refers to the tendency of the atmosphere to enhance or suppress vertical motions of the air. Under conditions of atmospheric instability, the **vertical growth of the fire's convective column** is facilitated and enhanced. This, in turn, enhances the burning rate of fuels at the surface. As the height and extent of the fire's convective column increase, so does the possibility of very strong, **erratic surface winds, fire whirls**, and other transient and often dangerous fire phenomena. When the atmosphere is sufficiently unstable, the vertical growth of the fire's convective column can trigger the formation of **pyroclouds**.

Concerning **drought**, although it is not a prerequisite for the occurrence of large wildfires, it nevertheless relates closely to the potential for the development of extreme fire behavior. This occurs most often when drought is combined with periods of increased atmospheric instability and/or strong winds. In addition, drought plays a key role in regulating the availability of fuels, affecting their flammability.

For a brief and more insightful overview of the role of weather in the ignition, spread, and behavior of wildfires, you can refer to FLAME's first promotional video, available at the following link:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RWFJYh-nAWA>

CRITICAL FIRE WEATHER PATTERNS OF GREECE

As with any other meteorological variable, changes in fire weather elements at the surface, where a wildfire ignites and spreads, are driven by large-scale movements and changes in the atmospheric air, which are an integral part of the general circulation of our planet's atmosphere. To put it simply, **local/regional fire weather** conditions are primarily determined by changes in the **arrangement of low/high-pressure systems** and the consequent **movement of air masses** with different properties (temperature, moisture).

The goal of synoptic pyrometeorology is to identify and link synoptic states of the atmosphere with fire danger and the potential for the development of extreme fire behavior. The concept is pretty simple. **Synoptic systems** (e.g., anticyclones, cyclones, upper-air disturbances) are typically **large** and **move/change slowly**, determining changes in fire weather conditions both at the surface and within the first few kilometers of the atmosphere. Therefore, by knowing which synoptic patterns can increase fire danger and potentially lead to extreme fire behavior, it is possible to estimate with high accuracy, **several days in advance**, changes in fire weather conditions.

In the context of FLAME’s WP2, we focused explicitly on this necessity. Exploiting high-resolution atmospheric reanalysis data (ERA5, 0.25° x 0.25°), retrieved from the European Centre for Medium-range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), and advanced machine learning techniques, we first compiled a prototype climatology of synoptic patterns affecting weather in Greece during the period May – October, for the reference period 1979 – 2020. Our initial analysis resulted in **36 synoptic patterns**, which were then

merged into **5 critical fire weather pattern groups** based on their specific characteristics (see image on the left). The definition of the critical fire weather pattern groups was carried out by linking the individual synoptic patterns with **different fire danger levels** and/or potential for the development of extreme fire behavior. To this end, we used high-resolution data from the Canadian Forest Fire Weather Index System (CFFWIS), retrieved from ECMWF.

The results of our analysis showed that each of the 5 critical fire weather patterns is associated with **distinct fire weather conditions** and, accordingly, with a **different level of fire danger** (see image below). At this point, it is important to note that beyond the critical fire weather patterns themselves, **transitions from one pattern to another** are of particular importance as they can significantly increase fire danger and promote the development of extreme fire behavior. For example, during the catastrophic **August 2021** wildfires in Greece, a **transition from pattern 4 to pattern 3** was recorded: the ignition and initial spread of the fire took place under extremely dry and hot conditions, with atmospheric instability occurring later, leading eventually to the formation of pyroclouds and the development of extreme fire behavior.

CRITICAL FIRE WEATHER PATTERNS - GREECE

| FIRE DANGER |
|--|---|---|---|---|---|
| 1 | Much cooler weather | Much moister weather | Weak winds | Stability | Very low |
| 2 | Cooler weather | Moister weather | Weak winds over E Greece
Strong winds over W Greece | Stability | Low |
| 3 | Warmer weather | Drier weather | Strong winds over SE Greece | Instability | Moderate/High over W & N Greece
High/Very high over S & E Greece |
| 4 | Much warmer weather | Much drier weather | Weak winds | Stability | High/Very high |
| 5 | Warmer weather | Drier weather | Very strong winds over E Greece | Stability | Very high/Extreme |

LIGHTNING-IGNITED WILDFIRES: A LURKING THREAT?

Lightning strikes are the major cause of the **natural ignition** of wildfires around the globe, while in some regions they produce the largest amount of wildfires. Studies have shown that lightning strikes produce **almost 5 %** of total forest fires in the **Mediterranean** and are one of the most important precursors of the largest forest fires during the fire season. The reason that lightning can cause a wildfire is due to its **temperature** which can exceed **27.000 degrees Celsius** (5 times hotter than the surface of the sun). Lightning-ignited wildfires are associated with the occurrence of **dry thunderstorms**.

A **dry thunderstorm** can be defined as a thunderstorm that produces **lightning strikes** between the cloud and the ground and is accompanied by **small amounts of precipitation**. The atmospheric conditions that are prone to the development of dry thunderstorms include **elevated atmospheric instability** and a very **deep dry lower tropospheric layer**, which under various circumstances will allow for the development of high-based convective clouds. The deep and dry lower tropospheric layer is a common characteristic of dry thunderstorms since it further promotes the **evaporation** of precipitation and thus increases the threat of lightning-ignited wildfires.

However, it should be noted that **not all dry thunderstorms** lead to wildfires. The ignition of a wildfire following a lightning strike depends also on the **type of fuel**, its **moisture content**, as well as **the fire weather conditions** at the surface during and after the lightning occurrence. For example, in case the **fuels** are **very dry** and thus **critically flammable**, and **fire weather** conditions are **favorable** for the spread of a wildfire (e.g. hot and dry conditions, enhanced surface winds) a

lightning strike can lead to a **wildfire** in a matter of a **few minutes**. On the other hand, in case the **fuels** are **sufficiently humid**, and **fire weather** conditions are **not favorable** for the spread of a wildfire, then **ignition** might take **multiple hours** or even **days** following the lightning strike until fire weather conditions allow for that. In this case, a lightning-ignited wildfire is a **lurking threat** that can spark anytime when the conditions become favorable.

The image on the left presents a simple conceptual model of fire ignition following a lightning strike. Initially, lightning strikes a tree and it “travels” through its core down to the roots. If there is a lot of humidity, the tree might not catch fire instantly. However, despite the lack of oxygen, the interior of the tree and its roots can still catch fire, leading to internal and slow combustion that is hard to detect without the use

of thermal cameras or other remote sensing techniques. Finally, if fire weather conditions allow for it (e.g. hot and dry conditions, enhanced winds, increased flammability of fine dead fuels around the tree), the fire inside the tree can expand outside and ignite a wildfire.

As recent studies have shown, lightning-ignited wildfires are also relatively frequent in Greece. Recent examples of such events are the wildfires that broke out in Skopelos Island on 6 and 18 June 2022, as well as the wildfire in Agio Oros on 29 June 2022. The wildfires in Skopelos on 6 June 2022 ignited right after fast-moving dry thunderstorms impacted the island with numerous lightning strikes. However, fire weather conditions were not favorable for rapid fire spread and these wildfires were contained fast. On the other hand, the wildfire that ignited on 18 June 2022 was caused by thunderstorms that impacted Skopelos island with multiple lightning strikes from 10-11 June 2022. Fire weather conditions during the thunderstorms and days after were associated with low to moderate fire danger. However, on 18 June, fire weather conditions deteriorated and a wildfire broke out. In this case, fire weather conditions resulted in a more

rapid fire spread, and more effort was required to fully contain the wildfire. The lightning-caused wildfire in Agio Oros on 29 June 2022 was caused by thunderstorms that impacted the area either on June 23 or June 28 with numerous lightning strikes. In this case, significant effort was required to fully contain the fire.

FLAME PUBLICITY FACTS

Publications in peer-reviewed scientific journals

Dragozi E, Giannaros TM, Kotroni V, Lagouvardos K, Koletsis I (2021) Dead fuel moisture content (DFMC) estimation using MODIS and meteorological data: The case of Greece. *Remote Sensing* 13, 4224.

Giannaros TM, Papavasileiou G, Lagouvardos K, Kotroni V, Dafis S, Karagiannidis A, Dragozi E (2022) Meteorological analysis of the 2021 extreme wildfires in Greece: Lessons learned and implications for early warning of the potential for pyroconvection. *Atmosphere* 13, 475.

Conference posters and presentations

Giannaros TM, Papavasileiou G, Lagouvardos K, Kotroni V, Dafis S, Karagiannidis A, Dragozi E. Lessons learned from the extreme wildfires of early August 2021 in Greece. EGU General Assembly 2022, Vienna, Austria and online, 23-27 May 2022, EGU22-5727.

Giannaros TM, Papavasileiou G, Lagouvardos K, Kotroni V, Dafis S, Karagiannidis A, Dragozi E. The 2021 extreme wildfires in Greece: Lessons learned and implications for early warning of the potential for pyroconvective events. IAWF Fire & Climate – Impacts, Issues & Futures, Pasadena, California, USA and online, 23-27 May 2022. The recorded presentation can be found [here](#).

Papavasileiou G, Giannaros TM. An outbreak of pyroconvection during the catastrophic 2021 wildfires in Greece and its predictability. IAWF Fire & Climate – Impacts, Issues & Futures, Pasadena, California, USA and online, 23-27 May 2022. The recorded presentation can be found [here](#).

Papavasileiou G, Giannaros TM. The catastrophic 2021 wildfires in Greece: An outbreak of pyroconvective events. 3rd International Conference on Fire Behaviour and Risk, Alghero, Sardegna, Italy, 3-6 May 2022.

Giannaros TM, Papavasileiou G. The Varympompi 2021 (Athens, Greece) extreme wildfire: Insights from coupled fire-atmosphere numerical simulations. 3rd International Conference on Fire Behaviour and Risk, Alghero, Sardegna, Italy, 3-6 May 2022.

FLAME in the media

<https://www.kathimerini.gr/society/561920029/explainer-oi-mega-pyrkagies-stin-epochi-tis-klimatikis-krisis-ti-einai-kai-giati-antimetopizontai-dyskola/>

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